

CULTiVATE

Food Sharing in Dublin

Impact report

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Overview

31	Food sharing initiatives
24	Initiatives redistributing food, saving surplus food from disposal and providing food for those in need
10	Initiatives cooking and eating together , reducing loneliness and improving nutrition
15	Initiatives growing food , reducing spend on food for participants and creating opportunities for enhancing physical and mental wellbeing
16	Initiatives undertake multiple activities around food , contributing to a circular bioeconomy

Annual impacts at city scale*

Social	62,828 meals shared	
Economic	7 tonnes of food produced	
Environmental	3,925 tonnes CO₂e avoided	
Civic engagement	318 active volunteers improving their wellbeing	
Education	6,169 people learning via attending events	

*Food sharing initiatives (FSIs) in Dublin city centre with a website, social media profile or app, were identified with the [CULTIVATE](#) mapping tool. Impacts were calculated using [The Toolshed SIA](#), part of the [Food Sharing Calculator](#). There are FSIs which do not have their own digital profile, so these figures are likely to be underestimates of the total impacts created by FSIs across the city.

Executive Summary

FSIs are organisations that enable the collective growing, cooking, eating, and redistribution of food, as well as the exchange of food-related skills and knowledge and the sharing of spaces and devices. They are often community-driven food projects which create solutions to local needs and include community gardens, neighbourhood kitchens and a plethora of redistribution organisations. The [CULTIVATE](#) project has developed an assessment tool to help document and understand the sustainability impacts of these food sharing initiatives (FSIs) – [The Toolshed](#) – supporting FSIs, policy makers, food supply actors, researchers and citizens to enact a just transition to more sustainable and resilient urban food systems.

This report provides a set of sustainability impact scenarios for Dublin city, combining insights from CULTIVATE's automated [Food Sharing Map](#), which locates and classifies FSIs, with sustainability impact assessment (SIA) data submitted by FSIs. These scenarios provide low, average and high estimations of the sustainability impacts created by FSIs. As more FSIs submit SIA data, these estimations of sustainability impact at the urban scale will become more accurate. It should be noted that the impact indicators presented in this report are only a subset of the total impacts these initiatives create. The [Talent Garden](#) includes a range of SIA reports from FSIs that illustrate the full breadth of impact. Individually, FSIs often deliver significant and multifaceted benefits that extend beyond what can be captured in quantified metrics.

Key Insights

- Dublin has a lower density of food sharing initiatives (FSIs) compared to the cities of Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht, indicating significant scope for growth.
- Levels of civic engagement in Dublin's FSIs are also lower than in these other cities, suggesting opportunities to strengthen participation and community involvement.
- The range of impacts from Dublin's FSIs align closely with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are broadly comparable to those seen in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht.
- At the city scale, Dublin's FSIs collectively contribute to multiple sustainability outcomes:
 - Social Impact: **62,828 meals** shared
 - Economic Impact: approximately **seven tonnes** of food produced
 - Environmental Impact: **3,925 tonnes of CO2e** avoided
- Across 31 FSIs, an estimated 214 events were hosted, engaging around 6,169 attendees and supporting education, skills development, and wider community participation.
- The distribution of FSIs varies by activity. Initiatives that include redistribution are located mostly in the north inner city, followed by the south inner city. FSIs that include food growing are mostly found within the inner city, as are initiatives that incorporate cooking and eating.

How to use this report

- **As an evidence base:** This report provides a baseline on which to map, track and monitor sustainability impacts from FSIs across the city over time.
- **For policy evaluation:** This report demonstrates where FSI impacts align with existing policies, including national, local, and international measures.
- **To identify progress towards local and global sustainability goals:** This report highlights how Dublin's FSIs contribute to social, economic and environmental sustainability in ways that align with Dublin City Council (DCC) priorities and broader UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) themes.

Food Sharing in Dublin

As part of the [CULTIVATE](#) project, FSIs in Dublin with a digital trace (website, app, or social media profile) were located using the CULTIVATE Food Sharing Map (due to launch in January 2026, and hosted on [Sharing Solutions](#)). The map uses a large language model, supported by the [European Food Sharing Dictionary](#), to identify and classify FSIs, activities often overlooked by conventional business directories. It is interactive, open access, and underpinned by manual checks for accuracy, providing Dublin City Council with a robust evidence base to understand the distribution and nature of FSIs, to engage more effectively with these initiatives, and to assess their contribution to local food, health, and sustainability priorities (see Figures 1, 3, 4 and 5 below).

Figure 1. All FSI locations currently shown on the Food Sharing Map (October 2025).

In total, 31 validated FSIs were identified in Dublin through the map, which assigned them a category of activity. (see Appendix A). Many engage in more than one type of activity (for example, combining growing with distribution, or cooking with distribution). Just over half of all FSIs in Dublin are multifunctional.

Figure 2 FSI activities showing multifunctionality, with the number of FSIs in each category indicated in green

Sixteen initiatives engage in more than one type of activity. Of these, nine both grow and redistribute food, five cook or eat and redistribute, and two undertake all three activities. Fifteen FSIs engage in growing activities (Figure 3), ten in cooking and eating (Figure 4), and twenty-four in the (re)distribution of food (Figure 5).

Figure 3. Growing FSIs

Figure 4. Cooking & Eating FSIs

Figure 5. (Re)distribution FSIs

As the automated mapping process improves, more FSIs develop distinct digital traces, and additional FSIs submit impact data, the accuracy of future estimates will increase. Annual updates of the mapping data will continue through 2030, progressively building a more comprehensive picture of the evolving food sharing landscape in Dublin. The Food Sharing Map will also include a feature for users to suggest FSIs that may be missing, helping to crowdsource updates and ensure broader coverage. The figures below illustrate the activities of the FSIs identified (Figure 6), how they share - through barter, collection, selling, or gifting (Figure 7).

In Dublin, food sharing is dominated by redistribution, with 24 initiatives including this activity in their operations. In general, most FSIs are located within the inner city, with fewer and more dispersed FSIs on the periphery of the city. This leaves large areas of the city without any FSI present. While some FSIs are mobile, operating in a range of locations across the city, this distributional imbalance requires attention to ensure local needs are being addressed. The absence of organised peer-to-peer collecting or bartering initiatives suggests that such exchanges play a more limited role in the city’s food sharing landscape than elsewhere, at least in terms of formalised FSIs.

Figure 6. FSI involvement in different activities

Figure 7. Modes of food sharing.

Estimating impacts from FSIs in Dublin

City-scale FSI impacts are based on data from validated FSIs, identified using the Food Sharing Map from across different categories of food sharing (i.e. growing, cooking and eating, redistribution or a combination). This dataset includes key impact data from our CULTIVATE FSI project partner, FoodCloud, who conducted an extensive [sustainability impact assessment](#) (SIA) using The Toolshed within the Sharing Solutions platform. FoodCloud isolated Dublin data from nationwide sustainability efforts to generate a picture of their food sharing impact within the Dublin urban and peri-urban region. All other validated FSIs were contacted to ascertain their key impacts and scale. An initial response rate of 58% was achieved, rising to 61% after follow-up. Not all FSIs provided complete data on scale or key impacts nonetheless this gives a robust sample of the FSI population that is useful for more accurately estimating the sustainability impacts across all mapped FSIs in the city.

To ensure that Dublin’s food sharing impacts were not overstated at city level, an additional step was introduced to account for organisational scale. This refinement builds on the approach first developed in the [previous research phase](#). Another refinement in the FSI categorisation process for Dublin, involved a more nuanced assessment of primary activity (see [Appendix A](#)), ensuring that overlapping functions were captured without overestimating total impacts. The approach produces a conservative yet representative estimate of food sharing activity across Dublin.

During the categorisation process, considerable overlap was observed between the three main areas of activity: growing, cooking and eating, and distribution (as shown above in Figure 2). To avoid double counting, each FSI was assigned to a single core category representing its primary mode of activity. Where initiatives were clearly multifunctional and operating across two core categories equally, they were retained as such, with their associated values divided evenly (50/50) between the relevant categories. This ensured that overall participation across activity domains remained representative, while avoiding duplication in the calculation of Dublin’s aggregate sustainability impacts. Each reallocation was informed by a review of individual FSI activity profiles. This process provides a transparent and conservative estimate of impacts across Dublin’s food sharing landscape.

Methodological Steps

1. **Mapping** – Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) across Dublin were identified and mapped using the Food Sharing Map.
2. **Surveying** – Validated Dublin FSIs were surveyed to collect data on key sustainability impact indicators and organisational size.
3. **Weighting** – A size-weighting adjustment was applied to the impact values collected in Step 2. This adjustment, made before averaging, improved representativeness in subsequent calculations (see Table 1).
4. **Averaging** – Weighted averages were calculated for each type of FSI activity (Growing, Cooking & Eating, and Distribution) using the survey data.
5. **Scaling** – City-level estimates were then produced by multiplying the weighted average impact per activity type by the number of FSIs from each **reallocated** category, generating a baseline estimate of total annual impact for Dublin’s food sharing sector (see Table 2)

Table 1. Weighting applied to account for scale.

Organisational Scale	Linear weighting	Inverse- Adjusted weighting
Micro	0.25	1
Small	0.5	0.7
Medium	0.75	0.4
Large	1	0.25

An inverse-adjusted weighting was applied to account for larger FSIs and ensure smaller initiatives were proportionately reflected in the results. The weighting is inverted and adjusted so that the small initiatives do not remain at 0.5, effectively remaining static in their impact.

Table 2. City-level impacts weighted to account for FSI size with category reallocation.

FSI Category	Adjusted No. of FSIs involved in the activity	Weighted Average Impact per FSI (annual)	Estimated City-Level Impact (annual total)	Impact Metric
Cooking & Eating	7.5	8,377	62,828	Meals shared
Growing	13	.538	7	Tonnes of food produced
Redistribution	10.5	116,816 kg (*3.2 carbon conversion/1000)	3,925	Tonnes CO ₂ e avoided
All	31	199	6,169	Attendees at events
	31	10	318	Volunteers engaged

Following reallocation, and accounting for multifunctional initiatives, the final category totals were adjusted as shown below.

Table 3. Counting multifunctional FSIs 1

Food Sharing Initiative (FSI) activity type	Number after reallocation
Growing	13
Cooking and eating	6
Redistribution	9
Multifunctional (Cooking & Redistribution)	3
Total	31

To account for multifunctional initiatives, the three multifunctional FSIs were split evenly between the two relevant categories (1.5 allocated to each). This produced the following adjusted totals used in the city-level impact calculations:

Table 4. Counting multifunctional FSIs

Adjusted category totals (after 50/50 split)	Number used for scaling
Growing	13
Cooking and eating	6 + 1.5 = 7.5
Redistribution	9 + 1.5 = 10.5
Total (effective)	31

Comparing FSI impact scenarios internationally

In environmental policy, decisions are often based on limited or uneven data. For instance, [UNEP \(2021\)](#) highlights that global food waste figures rely on extrapolating from a few countries, sometimes using outdated or inconsistent information. In the same way, data on the sustainability impacts of FSIs presented in this report should be understood as indicative. In this section we compare FSI impact scenarios in Dublin with scenarios created for Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan, this time using unweighted figures, and without a category reallocation, in order to compare cities using the same approach adopted in these cities during the [previous research](#) phase. Four key indicators are used:

- **Food produced** in tonnes – for initiatives that include growing
- **Number of meals shared** – for initiatives that include cooking and eating
- **Carbon emissions reduced** through diversion of food from disposal – for initiatives that include (re)distribution
- **Number of people volunteering** – for all FSIs

Reported impact values from all four cities were first aggregated to calculate a shared average impact per FSI for each indicator. This provided a common baseline for comparison across cities. For each impact scenario, the minimum, average, and maximum values were then multiplied by the adjusted number of FSIs mapped within each impact category in each city. Multifunctional FSIs were evenly divided across the three categories (a blunt but necessary adjustment to account for cross-cutting activities). This approach enabled the estimation of total city-scale impacts under low-, average-, and high-impact scenarios using a consistent, aggregated dataset.

As Table 5 illustrates, the gap between low and high sustainability impact scenarios is large across all cities. For example, estimated food production in Dublin ranges from 13 tonnes to 297 tonnes annually. FSI size influences outcomes, though impact is not always linked to scale. Often the goal of FSIs which incorporate growing is not to maximise production but to focus on social cohesion through acts of growing together with others, providing a welcoming third space for creating greater community integration. See [Sharing Solutions' Talent Garden](#) for illustrations of the diverse impacts growing FSIs can create.

These figures are based on key data submitted through 12 SIA reports from FSIs in Milan, Barcelona, and Utrecht, as well as data from 13 surveyed FSIs in Dublin and one full SIA report from our FSI partner, FoodCloud.

While context-specific factors have shaped each city's FSI landscape, the current data suggest that Dublin underperforms compared to the other European cities, with fewer FSIs and smaller impacts across most categories except redistribution. The comparatively strong performance in redistribution reflects the inclusion of FoodCloud, which is a large FSI operating nationally and internationally. Even though only its Dublin activities are captured here, its impacts underscore a key strength within the city's FSI landscape.

Table 5 Comparative FSI sustainability scenarios using unweighted data

Indicator categories & UPU location	Impact Scenarios	Low	Average	High
Economic: Contribution to food production (tonnes)				
Barcelona		114	781	2,692
Utrecht		54	369	1,272
Milan		43	292	1,007
Dublin		13	86	297
Social: Meals shared (number of meals shared)				
Barcelona		2,283	201,704	548,800
Utrecht		1,400	123,673	336,490
Milan		1833	161,952	440,642
Dublin		417	36,807	100,146
Environmental: Reducing carbon footprint of the food system (amount in t CO₂e)				
Barcelona		11,605	70,604	154,389
Utrecht		3,072	18,689	40,867
Milan		4,949	30,111	65,899
Dublin		1707	10383	22704
Governance: volunteering (number of people)				
Barcelona		4,310	12,148	24,973
Utrecht		1,794	5,057	10,396
Milan		2,087	5,882	12,091
Dublin		605	1,704	3,503

Discussion

Urban food system sustainability is a growing international priority. Key reports highlight the crucial role of cities in responding to climate change ([IPCC, 2025](#)) and in strengthening food security and resilience ([FAO, 2025](#); [HLPE-FSN, 2025](#)). Cities worldwide are increasingly organising themselves through international networks, such as the [MUFPP](#), to pursue more just and sustainable urban food systems. New governance structures, such as local food policy councils, are emerging internationally to coordinate and deliver sustainable urban food plans ([Nunes and Lamine, 2025](#); [Michel, 2022](#)). As a MUFPP signatory, Dublin is well-positioned to build on this momentum. Establishing a food policy council, or similar participatory mechanism, would allow the city to harness local expertise, connect with international best practice, and demonstrate leadership in shaping a more resilient and equitable food future. At the same time, the local context highlights why such governance innovations matter. With cost-of-living pressures persisting, the risk of food poverty is rising ([Liffey Partnership, 2025](#)), driven in part by high rents and land values. In this environment FSIs provide vital mechanisms to improve food security, support local growing and urban green space, and reduce waste.

Three key and interrelated areas for action should be considered by Dublin City Council:

1. Strengthening and expanding FSI landscapes

Dublin has the fewest number, and lowest density, of FSIs among the cities compared. With just one FSI per 19,120 people, it lags behind Milan (1 per 11,738), Barcelona (1 per 7,493), and Utrecht (1 per 4,255). This makes it harder for Dublin to meet local needs, contribute to the SDGs and ensure a just and resilient food system for its citizens. These numbers highlight a provision gap in relation to FSIs in Dublin. To match Utrecht's number of FSIs per head of population, Dublin would require 108 additional FSIs. However, setting targets for expanding FSI numbers in Dublin should go beyond quantity and reflect the specific needs of local populations, recognising the full range of impacts that FSIs create. This requires interdepartmental collaboration to share data related to population needs in the city and an organising structure to discuss findings and create action plans. Food policy councils have been shown to provide a multistakeholder forum to achieve such goals internationally.

2. Planning for urban-peri-urban (UPU) food resilience

FSIs support social, economic and environmental impacts making them a valuable part of a resilient urban food system. However, a lack of specific food policy and officers with food as a key responsibility at the local level in DCC impedes action for a just and resilient food system. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the vulnerability of UPU food systems to shocks like climate change, health crises, and global conflict. Many food sharing initiatives (FSIs) were forced to close during this time as they were considered non-essential services, yet they were providing essential supports, particularly to vulnerable and marginalised groups. The connection FSIs have to local populations was recognised during emergency planning by the central government. FSIs frequently had better local knowledge of those at risk than municipal departments ([Rut & Davies, 2024](#)). Understanding the landscape of FSIs and their impacts would help Dublin City Council plan for future disruptions by estimating the range of scope of potential impacts that would result from future closure of community gardens, kitchens and redistribution initiatives. It can also inform more strategic responses to ensure resilience in the sector in advance of any such risks materialising.

3. Meeting food waste reduction targets

[European regulations](#) now require a 30% per capita reduction in food waste, creating strong policy drivers for FSIs, especially redistribution initiatives. The sustainability impact scenarios can help municipal officers identify how much redistribution FSIs are diverting at the city scale, based on current capacity. Such estimates indicate how much the sector would need to grow to meaningfully contribute to national targets. City-level sustainability impacts from FSIs can be fed into national and local policy assessments for progression towards the SDGs supporting strategic planning.

Table 6 below indicates how FSIs contribute to policies both national and local and to wider efforts to support just transitions to more sustainable and resilient urban food systems.

Table 6. FSI contributions to policy objectives

Scale	Policy	FSI contribution
National	National Food Poverty Action Plan (Government of Ireland, 2022)	FSIs emerge as vital community-led approaches to tackling food poverty, aligning with the Food Poverty Action Plan launched in July 2024. They complement the plan’s intent to enhance access to nutritious food, engage affected communities, and integrate supports across sectors.
	National Obesity Strategy (Government of Ireland, 2016; 2025)	FSIs, by offering access to locally grown, nutritious food and encouraging active participation in food-growing and sharing, support key aims of Ireland’s national obesity policy, including health promotion, improved dietary habits, and enabling community engagement around healthy living.
Local	DCC Edible Dublin (Dublin City Council, 2024)	Through their community-based food systems work, FSIs support the goals of Dublin City Council’s Edible Dublin strategy, particularly: equitable access to nutritious food, strengthening urban food resilience, and promoting food skills and climate-sensitive food systems.
	Local Food Justice Work (Liffey Partnership, 2025)	Reports from local development companies, such as Liffey Partnership’s Spinning Plates, addressing food poverty in Ballyfermot and Cherry Orchard, show how community FSIs highlight the need for local responses to food poverty, linking directly to national debates on food justice, accessibility, dignity, and the National Food Poverty Action Plan.
	Local Food Policy development framework (Talamh Beo, 2023)	FSIs contribute directly to the priorities set out in Talamh Beo’s Local Food Policy Framework for Ireland, which emphasises community-based food initiatives as central to building fairer, more sustainable food systems. By advancing food sovereignty, supporting agroecological practices, and strengthening local food networks, FSIs reinforce the framework’s vision for resilient, just, and climate-conscious food futures.

While this report focuses on just four quantifiable indicators, the sustainability impacts of FSIs extend far beyond these areas. Their contributions to social cohesion, skills development, wellbeing, and community resilience are harder to capture, yet remain integral to the value they create. These qualitative and often transformative impacts must be recognised alongside the quantified results presented here. Realising these wider benefits depends on enabling conditions: access to space,

adequate investment, government support, and strong community engagement. When these factors are in place, FSIs can amplify their contributions across multiple dimensions, from local food production and lower CO₂ emissions to stronger community ties.

To date, Dublin has taken a cautious regulatory stance, particularly towards surplus food redistribution, citing health and safety concerns around grassroots food action groups, and more broadly towards food sharing activities. This risk-averse approach has constrained the operational space for FSIs, limiting certain modes of sharing, with no collection or bartering FSIs identifiable or validated, in contrast to practices evident in other Hub cities. Milan illustrates how a more enabling local authority approach can strengthen the role of FSIs. The city's Food Policy Department has formalised collaboration between redistribution organisations and other food system actors, consolidating efforts through the [creation of Food Help Hubs](#). These hubs emerged from coordinated action between the municipality, a regional business association (Assolombarda), an academic partner (PoliMi), and an anti-poverty initiative (Ricetta QuBi), and a private foundation (Fondazione Cariplo). Together, they demonstrate how structured local authority support can help FSIs scale their activities, extend their reach, and align more closely with wider sustainability and social policy goals.

Drawing on these lessons, alongside the scenarios, goals, and policy alignments presented in this report, Dublin now has an opportunity to consider how FSIs might further contribute to city-scale sustainability impacts.

Conclusion

This report summarises CULTIVATE's efforts to systematically map, survey, and quantify the city-wide impacts of Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) in Dublin. By combining impact data from a sample of verified initiatives, we piloted a method for estimating both the average and total sustainability impacts of diverse food sharing activities at the city level. Based on four quantifiable indicators, the results show that FSIs in Dublin collectively redistribute significant volumes of surplus food, produce fresh food in community gardens, and create thousands of shared meals each year. Beyond material outputs, they mobilise volunteers and generate wellbeing, social cohesion, and community engagement that extend beyond the scope of the metrics used. Our findings highlight that even micro- and small-scale initiatives, when aggregated, contribute meaningfully to city-wide goals alongside medium and large FSIs.

These insights have important implications for policy and practice. Regularised reporting, long-term and tailored investment, as well as spatially equitable distribution of support could help stabilise FSIs and enhance their contributions. Using this framework to systematically capture FSI activities would bridge the gap between community-level data and city-wide sustainability planning, ensuring that the contributions of FSIs are visible in official reporting and decision-making. More broadly, this research demonstrates the feasibility and value of assessing FSI impacts at the city scale.

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Appendix A - FSI list & activity categories

Name	Original	Re-allocated categories	Comment
	Growing = G Cooking & Eating = C Distribution =D		
Airfield Estate	G, C, D	G	Airfield submitted impact data on its growing activities
Bloomin' Crumlin	G	-	-
Bridgefoot Street Community Garden	G, D	G	Bridgefoot St (AKA Taplin's Fields) is primarily a growing initiative
Capuchin Day Centre	D	-	-
Cherry Orchard Community Garden	G, C, D	G	Primarily a growing initiative
Community Gardens Ireland	G, D	G	CGI represents growing initiatives
Community Roots	G, D	G	Primarily a growing initiative
Crosscare Café	C, D	C	Crosscare café is primarily a cooking initiative
Dublin City Council	G	-	-
Dublin Community Supported Agriculture	G, D	G	Primarily a growing initiative
Dublin Food Co-op	D	-	-
Dublin Northwest Partnership	G, D	G	Although multifunctional, this initiative has been allocated as primarily growing rather than distribution of surplus food, emphasis on its community garden.
Dublin Simon Community	C, D	C	Although multifunctional, this initiative has been allocated as primarily cooking & eating rather than distribution of surplus food.
Falling Fruit	G, D	D	Primarily a redistribution of surplus initiative
Flanagan's Fields Community Garden and Grow Dome	G, D	G	Primarily a growing initiative
Food Not Bombs	C, D	C/D	This initiative was split 50/50 over cooking and distribution
FoodCloud	D	-	-
Good Grub	D	-	-
Global Action Plan	G	-	-
Hardwicke Street Garden Club	G	-	-
HSE.ie (Healthy Food Made Easy)	C	-	-
Irish Seed Savers Association	G, D	D	This initiative was reallocated to distribution
Irish Soup Kitchen Centres Ltd	C, D	C/D	This initiative was split 50/50 over cooking and distribution
Little Flower Penny Dinners	D	C	This initiative was reallocated to cooking and eating category, it submitted impact data on its shared meals
Meals on Wheels Home	C, D	C/D	This initiative was split 50/50 over cooking and distribution
Northside Partnership	D	-	-
Seed Sovereignty	G, D	G	Primarily a growing initiative
Slow Food Ireland	C	-	-
Society of St. Vincent de Paul	D	-	-
South Dublin County Partnership	C	-	-
The D.8 Food Bank	D	-	-

Appendix B - Notes on scale

FSI Name	Activities	Regular volunteers	Full Time	Part Time	Head count	Size per FT	Size per HC	FINAL CATEGORISATION including external support factors such as grants & funding	Weighting	Inverse Adjusted Weighting
*Airfield Estate	Growing, Cooking, Distribution	5	15	7	27.5	Small	Small	Large	1	0.25
*Little Flower Penny Dinners	Cooking & Eating, Distribution	15	15	3	33.5	Small	Small	Small	0.5	0.7
*Bloomin Crumlin'	Growing	35	0	0	35	N/A	Small	Small	0.5	0.7
*Crosscare	Cooking & Eating, Distribution	15	15	3.5	33.5	Small	Small	Small	0.5	0.7
*Global Action Plan	Growing	35	15	0	50	Small	Medium	Medium	0.75	0.4
*Taplin's Fields Community Garden (formerly Bridgefoot st)	Growing, Distribution	15	0	0	15	N/A	Micro	Micro	0.25	1
*(NorthDublin Partnership) Health Food Made Easy	Cooking & Eating	5	15	15	35	Small	Small	Small	0.5	0.7
*(Liffey Partnership) Community Food & Nutrition Worker	Cooking & Eating	5	15	7.5	27.5	Small	Small	Small	0.5	0.7
*Chapelizod Allotments	Growing	35	0	0	35	N/A	Small	Micro	0.25	1
*FoodCloud	Distribution	35	15	15	65	Small	Medium	Large	1	0.25
*Dublin Food Co-Op	Distribution	35	1	11	47	Micro	Small	Micro	0.25	1
Meals on Wheels Network**	Cooking & Eating	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Medium	0.75	0.4
Capuchin Day Centre**	Distribution	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Small	0.5	0.7
Falling fruit**	Growing, Distribution	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Micro	0.25	1

*Responded to survey with validated scale.

**Assigned an estimate scale based on publicly available data